

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Qulmatov Qurvonali Zokirali o'g'li

ROUND ROBIN REJALASHTIRISH ALGORITMIDA JARAYONLARNING

O'RTACHA KUTISH VAQTINI HISOBLASH

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/MAY

